

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

A machine learning approach to violin timbre quality classification

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September 2018

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Acknowledgement

I would first like to thank Ph.D. Sergio Giraldo, who was always open, available and who always adapted to my schedule. He has made this thesis possible and has constantly guided me to improve my decisions.

I would also like to thank Ph.D. Rafael Giraldo, for supporting this thesis since the beginning, and all the MTG members that have supported this master, offering a huge help and sharing a lot of knowledge about music technology and sound processing.

Finally, I must express my very profound gratitude to my family and my dear people, that have been there when I needed an extra support. Thank you.

Pedro.

Abstract

Timbre definition has been traditionally unclear and it is difficult to find a precise definition related to timbre attributes, since several factors contribute to its perception. In this thesis, we present a machine learning approach to automatically classify expert defined timbral attributes, by extracting audio features from violin recordings. Features were extracted using the ESSENTIA library and machine learning models were obtained to classify the aforementioned timbre attributes. Automatic feature selection tools were used to study the most relevant features for classification. Results might indicate that the extracted audio features contain sufficient information to correctly classify the studied timbral attributes.

Keywords: Timbre; Violin; MIR, Machine Learning; Feature Selection

Chapter 1

Introduction

Music, according to Cambridge Dictionary, is a pattern of sounds made by musical instruments, voices, or computers, or a combination of these, intended to give pleasure to people listening to it. Despite this definition, music has traditionally been considered as art, and it is hardly related to expression of feelings and communication. It has been studied that instrument practicing increase brain activity performance, activating both brain hemispheres, improving concentration, memory and discipline capacity, due to during music learning, brain is challenged by performing several tasks at the same time (Habibi et al., 2018).

This thesis project is within the project TELMI, 2016 (TELMi stands for Technology Enhanced Learning of Musical Instrument Performance). TELMI is a Research and Innovation action coordinated by MTG-UPF and funded by the European Commission. The partner institutions involved are: Universitat Pompeu Fabra, University of Genova, Royal College of Music, HIGHSKILLZ, and SAICO INTELLIGENCE, S.L.

The general objectives of the TELMI project are:

1. to design and implement new interaction paradigms for music learning and training based on state-of-the-art multi-modal (audio, image, video, and motion) technologies,
2. to evaluate the pedagogical effectiveness of such new paradigms,

3. to develop new multi-modal, interactive music learning prototypes for student-teacher, student only, and collaborative learning scenarios,
4. to create a publicly available reference database of multimodal recordings for online learning and social interaction among students.

The results of the project will serve as a basis for the development of next generation music learning systems, thereby improving on current student-teacher interaction and student-only practice, providing the potential to make music education and its benefits accessible to a substantially wider public.

1.1 Motivation

Musical performance quality evaluation is complicated due to its subjectivity, but in music teaching, there is a certain consensus on some aspects of musical performance, such as pitch stability or dynamic stability, that can be easily evaluated when the piece is known. Timbre goodness, on the contrary, is difficult to measure due to the complexity of timbre itself. Several factors contribute to timbre such as human perception or the room acoustics, and there is no clear consensus about how to quantify timbre performance. If we think about pitch, for example, we can probably measure a clear distance between the desired pitch and the performed pitch measured in Hertz, but regarding to timbre, its evaluation is much more complex. No good or bad timbre can be assessed by itself since it will depend on the situation, the performer, the context and even the listener, so quantitative feedback about timbre is far from being commonly given.

Instead of quantifying timbre, due to this lack of consensus, musicians tend to use common words in order to give a qualitative feedback about the music excerpt, and these words may vary among instruments, languages or teachers as vary the common language itself. These timbre feedback attributes are not particularly matched to what a good or bad timbre is. If the attribute used to describe the timbre of a given excerpt is, for example, "cold", we cannot say if it is good or bad if we don't previously know the intention of the composer or the performer. For that reason,

these attributes are subjective to the performer and if the player is not used to the set of timbre attributes that are being used in the current context, he/she may misunderstand the given feedback.

1.2 Objectives

The hypothesis of this thesis is that audio descriptors might contain enough information to make feasible a classification model that correctly separate timbre attributes. Consequently, the objective of this thesis is to build a model that properly classify timbre attributes by using audio features extracted from recorded audio.

The specific objectives are as follows:

- To create a tagged database of extracted audio descriptors and timbre attributes
- To develop a workflow from tagged raw audio to the aforementioned database
- To set up a repository with all the code clearly written and commented for further use
- To automate processes and functions to ease future research
- To build models that predict timbre attributes from raw audio
- To analyze the audio descriptors that better describe timbre attributes

1.3 Structure of the Report

After this introduction section, a state of the art of the thesis is being reviewed regarding to timbre as a sound dimension and a technological approach of timbre too, focusing on features extraction and machine learning. Afterwards, the audio dataset and all the tools used for the development of this thesis project are being presented. At this point, the methodology of the procedures for the project are explained; first, the preprocessing and the extraction of the audio features and,

then, the machine learning approach. Achieved results, conclusions, contribution and future work follow up this report. The last section of this thesis consists on two appendixes about the used algorithms during the development of this thesis.

Chapter 2

State of the art

To study the connection between timbre features extracted from the audio excerpts and the semantic timbral attributes that are used among musicians, two main topics need to be reviewed: timbre as a sound dimension, and its technological approach. These topics will be reviewed in this section.

2.1 Timbre: definition and subjectivity

Traditionally, musical notes have been defined by a few dimensions (varying depending on the author) regarding to pitch, timbre and dynamics. Even though definitions related to pitch or dynamics have been well established (e.g. pitch stability or attack), it is difficult to find a precise definition related to timbre attributes, since several factors contribute to its perception, and it is frequently defined as what differentiates two sounds with the same pitch, loudness and duration, as explained in *Perceptual scaling of synthesized musical timbres: Common dimensions, specificities, and latent subject classes* (McAdams et al., 1995). Although this lack of clear definition, being often defined by what it is not (pitch, harmony, etc.), Eerola, 2011, deepened on this topic and assumed that there is a great deal about its psychological representation. In their aim of making automatic decisions about single notes quality, they used timbre attributes, among others, to test if it is possible to train a classifier using extracted audio features to make note quality judgement consistent with humans’

judgements.

During the last decades, numerous studies on musical timbre have tried to represent timbre by significant perceptual dimensions and their semantic associations. Most of these studies have concluded to deal with 3 or 4 perceptual dimensions for modelling monophonic timbre and have also proposed a wide range of attributes to label them. In these dimensions, different aspects of timbre are represented to build a model that tries to qualify and/or quantify timbre cues. Jensen, 1999 assumed the multidimensionality of timbre and he went further assuming that timbre models two different aspects of the sound: the identity of the sound and the expression of the sound. The identity of the sound is defined in that work as the timbre cues that make possible the identification of the instrument that produces that sound, the player or the location of the instrument. The expression of a sound is defined as the ability to differentiate a high-pitched piano from a soft piano, for instance, including parameters as pitch (the perceived note of the sound), the loudness (the perceived intensity of the sound) and the duration (perceived length of the sound). Moreover, he focused in other aspects of the timbre, as noise (of any instrument or any sound), roughness (measure of fast beats between two partials of the sound, closely related to dissonance-consonance), and the verbal attributes.

Some studies, revealed three or four perceptual dimensions. For example, Pratt and Doak, 1976, working with simple synthetic tones, proposed a three-dimensional space featuring vision (bright-dull), temperature (warm-cold) and wealth (rich-pure). Stepánek, 2006 made a multidimension scheme of the timbre too in Czech language, and has also resulted to four perceptual axes, one dimension related to vision (gloomy-clear), another one with texture (harsh-delicate), a third one with volume (full-narrow) and a last one with hearing (noisy/rustle-'undefined').

A multidimensional scaling from tags of artificial sounds with verbal attributes study was conducted by von Bismarck, 1974, and 4 axes were found too: the first associated with the verbal attribute pair dull-sharp, the second compact-scattered, the third full-empty and the fourth colorful-colorless. The dull- sharp axis was further found to be determined by the frequency position of the overall energy concentration of the

spectrum. The compact-scattered axis was determined by the tone/noise character of the sound. The other two axes were not attributed to any specific quality.

Related to that, it has been exposed that musicians tend to use natural language to communicate about timbre, and these used terms are subjective to the performer (Johnson and Gounaropoulos, 2006). To translate it to music, performers have to either have a very strong understanding of the underlying mechanisms that produce the sound, or a large amount of trial-and-error experience by generating timbral changes. Johnson and Gouaropoulos proposed a system that automatically classified the timbre by setting some values of timbre adjectives and then, the user, corrected these values with sliders to keep training the model. They used the following adjectives.

bright warm harsh hit plucked constant thick metallic woody

Fritz et al., 2007, in their work *Investigating English Violin Timbre Descriptors*, a set of timbre descriptors for violin was proposed. This list has been made by collecting all these terms from violins descriptions published in *The Strad* magazine between 1996 and 2007.

*alive balanced brash bright brilliant clean clear closed complex dark dead deep dull
even free full hard harsh heavy interesting light lively loud mellow metallic muffled
muted nasal not-penetrating open penetrating piercing powerful pure quiet raspy
resonant responsive rich ringing rough round sharp shrill singing smooth soft
sonorous steely strident strong sweet thin tinny tiny unbalanced uneven
unresponsive warm weak*

With all these common words, musicians try to suggest the auditory attributes of the timbre. McAdams and Giordano, 2008, in their aim to explain timbre as a multi-dimensional set of auditory attributes, they attempted to characterize quantitatively the ways in which sounds are perceived to differ. Early research on perceptual nature of timbre focused on the relative weights of different frequencies present in a

given sound (sound color), but in multidimensional scaling, no preconceptions about the physical or perceptual structure of timbre were made, so they studied the effects of pitch change on timbre relations, timbre as a vehicle for source identity, timbre intervals, timbre blend, the role of timbre in building and release of musical tension, among others. They concluded that timbre is a combination of continuous perceptual dimensions and discrete features to which listeners are sensitive, and they defended that these continuous dimensions often have quantifiable acoustic correlates. With the technological approach of timbre, these correlations are being followed to try to understand timbre better.

2.2 Technological approach of timbre

From a technological approach, we can extract a lot of features from audio excerpts to be related to timbre.

2.2.1 Features extraction

Music Information Retrieval (MIR) is the interdisciplinary science of retrieving information from music. As presented in *A large set of audio features for sound descriptors (similarity and classification) in the CUIDADO project*, a lot of information can be extracted from audio signals, and this information can be meaningful itself or can be barely interpreted (Peeters, 2004). Low-level descriptors are the first achieved information when extracting features from the raw audio. It allows us to get some information like the average loudness, the zero crossing rate or the spectral complexity, examples of attributes that can be extracted with ESSENTIA (Bogdanov et al., 2013). From these low-level features, much more complex attributes of a higher level can be computed, giving a semantic meaning to the calculated values, like tonal attributes (e.g.: tuning frequency estimation) or rhythmic characteristics (i.e.: beats per minute). Timbre features are more difficult to obtain due to the complex definition of timbre itself. In *Feature-based Characterization of Violin Timbre*, a set of features to analyze the timbre was proposed and it was composed by the four spectral moments, some spectral indicators (like brightness, or flatness),

harmonicity features (like tristimulus coefficients), MFCC (Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients), spectral contrast and some temporal features (like attack time) (Setragno et al., 2017). Despite of this set of features is only an example of a recent study features analysis, varying among the authors involved in this topic, most of them convey in using machine learning techniques to compute all the extracted data to try to find some relevant conclusion. This will be briefly reviewed on the next section.

2.2.2 Machine learning

Machine learning (ML), in the field of the artificial intelligence, is the learning ability of a computer without being explicitly programmed. Using ML, conclusions can be extracted by a machine with data that humans would last a lot of time to process, if so, and it is a valuable tool to match attributes from a given excerpt with its class. ML itself has a lot of algorithms and possible applications, but the goal of this thesis is not to deep into machine learning techniques. ML will be used to try to find some correlation between the features extracted from the audio excerpts and the semantic timbral attributes that are used among musicians. Three methods will be reviewed from studies that are related to the topic we are dealing with. The first one consists in a real-time system for measuring goodness in sound, based on wind instruments but the method is not instrument-dependent. The second work studies the efficiency of an advanced method applied to timbre analysis in general. The following one focuses on automatic assessment of trumpet quality base, and the fourth one is a study is about a feature-based characterization of violin timbre, a task considerably similar to the topic of this master thesis.

In *A real-time system for measuring sound goodness in instrumental sounds*, Picas et al., 2015, developed a tool that complements the typical tuner by evaluating sound quality. They recorded a collection of single notes played by professionals and used features extraction to compare this audio information to musician annotations and create a machine learning model. They recorded clarinet, flute and trumpet, and annotated the samples using the following classes: good sound, bad dynamic

stability, bad pitch stability, bad timbre stability, bad timbre richness and bad attack clarity. On the other hand, the system automatically detected the onsets, sustain, release and offset in order to segment the audio, and they used almost 200 features for each sound attribute. Then, they used a OneR classifier from WEKA to choose a single sound attribute for each class to compute the goodness score.

Knight et al., 2011, in *The potential for automatic assessment of trumpet tone quality*, examined the possibility of training ML algorithms to differentiate between the performance of good notes and bad notes. The dataset of this project was 239 notes played by 4 trumpet players and graded by 5 brass players. They worked on correlation between subjective ratings and audio extracted features. Individual notes were manually segmented to make discrete stimuli for subjective rating. For feature extraction, jAudio, 2006, was used and Automatic Classifier Engine was used for testing, training and running the classifier. Different ML algorithms were tried, as k-Nearest-Neighbours, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees and Neural Networks, and finally SVM was chosen.

A paper with a different point of view is *Timbre analysis of music audio signals with Convolutional Neural Networks* Pons et al., 2017, where the focus was to study the efficiency of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to learn about timbre representation from log-mel magnitude spectrograms. Since most of the timbre description techniques can be divided in bag-of-frames methods (modeling the statistics of the frequency content along several frames) and temporal modeling (representing spectro-temporal patterns), they explored modeling timbre by means of deep learning with magnitude spectrograms as the input of the system. They ran three general tasks based on timbre modeling to assess the validity of the strategy: singing voice phoneme classification, musical instrument recognition and music auto-tagging.

Setragno et al., 2017, in their work *Feature-based characterization of violin timbre* showed that it is possible to characterize violins from a low-level features perspective, using feature selection algorithms, reducing the number of features and obtaining a low-dimensional space where violins can be visualized. They recorded a set of 50 instruments (13 historical violins, 28 high-quality contemporary violins and 9

violins) from violin making school Instituto Antonio Stradivari. All recordings were performed by the same musician and the same bow. Afterwards, they analyzed some features of the signal: the four spectral moments (Centroid, Spread, Skewness, Kurtosis), other spectral indicators (Brightness, Roll-off, Flux, Irregularity, Flatness), features related to the distribution of harmonics (Tristimulus coefficients, Odd-Even ratio), two vectoral features describing the spectrum shape (Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients, MFCC, and Spectral Contrast) and some temporal features (Attack time, Attack slope, RMS energy and Zero-crossing rate). They used the Python Sklearn Toolbox (Grad, 2017) among other tried algorithms to compute feature selection and used t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) to reduce the dimensionality of the feature vectors. To conclude, they studied the feature selection results, they used a Support Vector Classifier to validate the model with a classification task, they validated the results with visualization since they could reduce enough the dimensionality of the feature vectors and, then, analyzed all these results to make a conclusion.

All these reviewed papers are very important to deeply understand the key points of the problem and had led to take some important decisions on how to manage audio signals, how to extract information from it, how to deal with feature selection or which classification algorithms should be tested.

Chapter 3

Materials

The materials used for this final thesis can be divided in the dataset of files that has been used to conduct the study and the open-source software tools to manage the audio files.

3.1 Dataset

The dataset is composed by 20 audio files of bowed violin audio stored in 44100 Hz at 16 bits per sample. Each file contains an example of the same score played evoking to each timbral attribute used. The 20 attributes are: dark, bright, cold, warm, harsh, sweet, dry, ressonant, light, heavy, grainy, pure, coarse, smooth, open, close, restricted, free, narrow and broad. The score is a set of 8 whole notes separated by silence. All the excerpts were recorded under the same conditions, including room, performer and microphone.

This dataset is original from the study *A Real-time Feedback Learning Tool to Visualize Sound Quality in Violin Performances* (Giraldo et al., 2017). The list of timbral attributes was defined by music educators that collaborated with the author.

Tone Study

Sergio Giraldo TELMI-UPF

Figure 1: Score of the recorded excerpts

3.2 Software

Some software tools has been used for the implementation of this project:

For general coding, preprocessing the signal and to link all the procedures, Python, 1994 has been used. Python is an open-source interpreted, interactive, object-oriented programming language that incorporates modules, exceptions, dynamic typing, very high level dynamic data types, and classes.

Music Information Retrieval has been performed using Essentia, 2013, an open-source C++ library with Python bindings for audio analysis and audio-based music information retrieval. Essentia is a collection of algorithms wrapped in a library, designed focusing on robustness, performance and optimality.

SonicVisualiser, 2013, has been used for audio signal visualization, and to check and correct some annotations. This tool is used to visualize audio characteristics, manually or automatically annotate excerpts, import and export annotation layers, play back audio files, and other useful operations related to data visualization. This software is open source.

It has been used Weka, 1993, that is an open source collection of machine learning algorithms for data mining tasks. Weka contains tools for data pre-processing, classification, regression, clustering, association rules, and visualization. It is also

well-suited for developing new machine learning schemes.

Jython, 1997, has been used to automate processes in Weka. Jython is an implementation of the high-level, dynamic, object-oriented language Python seamlessly integrated with the Java platform, specially designed for embedded scripting, interactive experimentation and rapid application development.

Chapter 4

Methodology

The development of this thesis started from 20 tagged audio files of 8 violin isolated notes, and the predominant timbral attribute of each audio is annotated as a meta-data tag. On the other hand, from the audio signal itself, several audio features can be extracted with the appropriate tools. Linking these complementary information, we can create a tagged database of extracted features. Once we have a database, a machine learning model can be built to obtain interesting information from it.

4.1 Music information retrieval

Music information retrieval has been used to extract the audio features from the recorded files to collect them in a database. Some steps needed to be done in order to be able to extract properly the needed information from the audio signal files.

The first step has been to isolate each note from each file, in order to extract audio features from each single note and it could be approached from two different methods: automatic segmentation or manual segmentation. When doing it automatically, it is possible to save a lot of time if it is correctly done, but the probability of having errors (i.e.: false detections, missing notes...) is quite high. On the other hand, if the notes isolation is done manually, this task could take too much time depending on the dataset dimensions. As far as two of this thesis objectives are to

develop a scalable workflow and create a tagged database, it has been automatically approached (to assure scalability) and it has been manually corrected, afterwards, to assure a trustworthy database.

The automatic isolation has been made by onset and offset detection using Onsets function from `Essentia.standard`. For the onset detection itself, the parameters of the Onsets function has been selected to obtain reasonably decent results. After some loops of parameters changing, it was decided to parametrize the function to skip as many onsets as possible, so an automatic correction subroutine was written to avoid a large number of false detections. After this automatic correction, results were pretty decent but some false detections and non-detected onsets still were in the results, so it was manually corrected using `SonicVisualiser`. To do that, the audio file was loaded onto `SonicVisualiser` and onsets were imported as an annotation layer. They have been manually corrected, and the final set of onsets were exported as "corrected onsets". The same procedure has been run to perform offset detection, but in this case, the input of the offset detection function has been the inverted signal of the audio file. Then, the onset times of the inverted audio had to be inverted again to perform as offsets of the original audio. With the correct set of onsets and offsets time stamps, notes were correctly isolated from one onset time stamp to its corresponding offset time stamp.

Figure 2: Automatically detected onsets and offsets example.

The manual correction of the onset and offset detections has been done to avoid false detection and to include some onsets and offset skipped by the function, but no posi-

tion correction has been done. The precision of the detected instants is not perfectly accurate, but it is fair enough to solve this particular problem. The maximum of autonomy of the automatic approach has been preserved for the reproducibility of the results and the scalability of the workflow.

Figure 3: Manually corrected onsets and offsets example.

Once the onset and offset detection have been run, all the single notes of the dataset are isolated, adding some extra margin at the beginning at the end of the note, due to that the database consists in isolated notes and it permitted to obtain all the information of the note. This margins were set manually, and are easily configurable, to be adaptable to future datasets. For each note global descriptors have been extracted and instant descriptors have been extracted too. The audio signal feature extraction task has been implemented using the Extractor algorithm from Essentia.standard. Global descriptors have been computed using the isolated notes as inputs, and extracting the descriptors that are able in this Essentia function.

Figure 4: Example of an isolated note after onsets and offsets corrections

Instantaneous descriptors were wanted to be extracted too, and to do that, each note

had to be divided onto smaller excerpts. A frame generator implemented in Essentia has been used and for each frame, the Essentia Extractor function has been run. All the extracted features has been saved in a .csv file in order to ease the visualization. Apart from that, .csv is a file format that can be used in Weka, and it is important for the machine learning approach explained in the next section.

To ease some procedures in next steps, different .csv files are created. On the one hand, one file collects all descriptors of all notes of all audios; this is our tagged descriptors database. Apart from that, we have 10 pair of attributes files, where descriptors of two contrary attributes are saved; it has simplified the way to use Weka for certain operations.

4.2 Machine learning approach

At this point, we were prepared to introduce the data into Weka to get some results for this thesis objectives. In this section we reviewed the database preparation, the attribute selection procedure and the timbral attribute classification. This Machine Learning approach has been based on pair of attributes classification: the whole database hasn't been tested since it wasn't the objective of the thesis, but trying to separate between contrary attributes (i.e. differentiate a "cold" sound from a "warm" one). Moreover, computational costs were unaffordable using a personal computer.

4.2.1 Database preparation

In the previous section, the data was collected into a database, and at this point, it needed to be checked, because one of the objectives of this thesis was to create a good database, and it had to be robust. The checking and modifications of the data can be divided into two important procedures.

The first modification in the database was done because of the magnitude of the data. From the beginning of experimenting with Weka, it was plain that there was a clear overfitting. The reason of that, was because comparing between a single pair

of contrary attributes, i.e. "cold" vs "warm", we had only 8 notes for each timbre class, and therefor, we only had 8 values for each global descriptor. Conceptually, these descriptors should be included in the workflow of the methodology because it would be very interesting to study how global descriptors could lead to significant predictions, but it couldn't be used with this particular dataset due to its size.

The second step of modifications was necessary to avoid some errors due to the values of the descriptors themselves, as for example, extremely broad range from lowest to highest value. To solve that, all the data has been normalized and then no errors appeared. It has been checked among several descriptors that the original and normalized data returned the same results.

4.2.2 Feature selection

After the reduction of the number of descriptors due to the mentioned reasons in the previous sections, 31 instantaneous audio features have been preserved. Depending on the size of the database, it could be a problem to compute classification algorithms with this number of descriptors using personal computers. For that reason, feature selection has been studied in order to analyze differences among different number of descriptors to solve classification problems.

For feature selection two different parameters need to be configured: the evaluator method and the search method. The evaluation method is a technique that evaluate each feature in the dataset and it returns a value in the context of the class variable. The search method is the technique that navigates among different combination of attributes in the dataset in order to return the list of chosen features. In the Appendix A, the search and evaluation methods that have been tested in this project are enumerated, including the description available in the Weka GUI.

A subroutine has been written in Jython to test different algorithms, be able to compare them in an easy way and visualize differences numerically and graphically. Given a pair of attributes database, different methods of feature selection could be selected. Afterwards, the subroutine is modifiable to use different number of

features, and the result of the specific classification method, number of features and feature selection algorithm, was represented.

Figure 5: Example of accuracy curve depending on the number of selected features.

A loop with all the number of features is run, and a curve of classification success is represented as in the figure 5. Another loop with different feature selection algorithms is computed on top, in order to visualize each feature selection algorithm curve, depending on the number of descriptors. Furthermore, for each algorithm and number of features, a summary is given as follows:

```
85.9666339549 % correct with 25 attributes.
Correctly Classified Instances      876      85.9666 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    143      14.0334 %
Kappa statistic                     0.704
Mean absolute error                  0.1488
Root mean squared error              0.3522
Relative absolute error              31.202 %
Root relative squared error          72.1166 %
Total Number of Instances           1019
=== Confusion Matrix ===
  a  b  <-- classified as
322 78 |  a = COLD
 65 554 |  b = WARM
```

No feature selection algorithm has been chosen as the best one since it is not the objective of this thesis, but some interesting results has been obtained that will be

discussed in the results chapter. Some encouraging results has been obtained related to feature selection being applied to automatic timbre assessment.

4.2.3 Classification

Classification methods has consisted on evaluate how classifier algorithms are able to differentiate between two contrary timbral attributes. As in the previous section, a subroutine has been written to test different algorithms and the results has been reviewed numerically and graphically. It has permitted to understand how classifiers perform to this particular problem.

Once some expertise has been obtained, two main tasks has been performed using classification algorithms: analyze some different algorithms and see how they perform, and compare classification accuracy among different number of features after feature selection.

The tested classification algorithms, based on rules classifiers, decision trees, logistic regressions and a SVM (support vector machine) algorithm; are specified in Appendix B and a description from Weka is included. A lot of time has been spent trying to guess the best algorithm, among the tested, to achieve good results, but after trying numerous scenarios, no specific algorithm seemed to perform significantly better than others. For that reason, the complexity of the model has tried to be kept low to maintain a reasonable computational cost and to not to waste time. If the complexity or the size of the database would change, this process should be repeated to evaluate the importance of the selected classification algorithm.

The second task involving classification algorithms, have been to evaluate the factor of the number of attributes in the classification task. To do that, from the feature selection algorithms, a ranking of the most important audio descriptors can be obtained. This ranking can be done using two different techniques: evaluating each audio descriptor by itself, or evaluating audio descriptors as a whole. Using the first technique, we could have a feature ranking as follows, and if we decide to use a number of features N , we only have to choose the N first features.

```

Evaluator:   weka.attributeSelection.InfoGainAttributeEval
Search:     weka.attributeSelection.Ranker -T -1.7976931348623157E308 -N -1

```

```

Relation:   ZOOM0006-ZOOM0007_norm
Instances:  1152

```

Ranked attributes:

```

0.52658    23 lowLevel.spectral_flux
0.36127     7 lowLevel.pitch
0.26173    26 lowLevel.spectral_rolloff
0.19381     6 lowLevel.hfc
0.19313    25 lowLevel.spectral_rms
0.19185    17 lowLevel.spectral_energy
0.18454    16 lowLevel.spectral_decrease
0.16255    14 lowLevel.spectral_complexity
0.16129    20 lowLevel.spectral_energyband_middle_high
0.1429     12 lowLevel.silence_rate_60dB
0.11172    18 lowLevel.spectral_energyband_high
0.11117    21 lowLevel.spectral_energyband_middle_low
0.09523    15 lowLevel.spectral_crest
0.07485    30 lowLevel.zerocrossingrate
0.06652    28 lowLevel.spectral_spread
0.06074     9 lowLevel.pitch_salience
0.04862     3 lowLevel.barkbands_skewness
0.03389    29 lowLevel.spectral_strongpeak
0.03142     2 lowLevel.barkbands_kurtosis
0.02884     4 lowLevel.barkbands_spread
0.0276     32 sfx.oddttoevenharmonicenergyratio
0.02414    19 lowLevel.spectral_energyband_low
0.02344    24 lowLevel.spectral_kurtosis
0.01884    22 lowLevel.spectral_flatness_db
0.01672    27 lowLevel.spectral_skewness
0.00204     1 Note
0          10 lowLevel.silence_rate_20dB
0          5 lowLevel.dissonance
0          13 lowLevel.spectral_centroid
0          8 lowLevel.pitch_instantaneous_confidence
0          31 sfx.inharmonicity
0          11 lowLevel.silence_rate_30dB

```

The second technique is a bit more complex, but it leads to a more reasonable result. In this case, the number of features N is selected before the attribute selection task, and the algorithm allows to use the set of N features, that combined, returns the best accuracy.

Using the same data and running a different type of evaluator and search method,

the result selecting 5 features is different to the previous selected features.

```
Evaluator:   weka.attributeSelection.CfsSubsetEval -P 1 -E 1
Search:      weka.attributeSelection.GreedyStepwise
-T -1.7976931348623157E308 -N 5 -num-slots 1
Relation:    ZOOM0006-ZOOM0007_norm
Instances:    1152
```

```
Selected attributes: 7,15,19,23,25 : 5
                    lowLevel.pitch
                    lowLevel.spectral_crest
                    lowLevel.spectral_energyband_low
                    lowLevel.spectral_flux
                    lowLevel.spectral_rms
```

In the context of trying to maintain the best classification accuracy by reducing the number of attributes, the second technique will provide always equal or better performance, since the best team of 5 is always better, or at most equal, than the best 5 put together.

As in the previous section, the best algorithm, set of attributes or accuracy have not been searched. Instead of that, after getting a ranking and using different number of features, some accuracies have been computed to give us some clues about the hypothesis of this thesis. After all, the purpose of this thesis is not to build the best machine learning model to fit to this particular problem, but to find relevant conclusions related to timbre using audio features from a wider perspective.

In the following section, some results are shown to overview the performance of the model and to perceive some clues about the objective of the thesis.

Chapter 5

Results

In this chapter, obtained results are being presented using the previously explained model examples. An overview of the importance of certain audio descriptors is evaluated while classifying among timbre attributes. Furthermore, an analysis and implication of using different number of features is revised.

5.1 Audio Descriptors Overview. Feature Selection

In this section, the audio features that have been used for timbre analysis are studied in the context of their importance in timbre classification tasks and their connection to timbre attributes.

Feature selection has been computed in each pair of attributes database using these settings:

Evaluator: Information Gain

Search Method: Ranker

Number of features: 5

If the information extracted from the 10 pair of attributes databases is collected, we can generate a general ranking focusing on which audio descriptors are being more used to separate between contrary timbral attributes. The number of features in

this example is 5, and it has been chosen for no special reason.

Table 1: Number of appearances selecting 5 features for each pair of attributes running feature selection in ten pair of attributes, using Information Gain as Evaluator and Ranker as a Search Method. Unused Features are not included in this table.

Feature	Times used (out of 10)
lowLevel spectral flux	6
lowLevel spectral rolloff	6
lowLevel hfc	5
lowLevel spectral energy	5
lowLevel spectral rms	5
lowLevel pitch	3
lowLevel spectral energyband high	3
lowLevel spectral centroid	2
lowLevel spectral decrease	2
lowLevel spectral energyband middle low	2
lowLevelspectral flatness db	2
lowLevel spectral skewness	2
lowLevel zerocrossingrate	2
lowLevel barkbands spread	1
lowLevel pitch instantaneous confidence	1
lowLevel spectral energyband middle high	1
lowLevel spectral kurtosis	1
lowLevel spectral strongpeak	1

As we can see in this general ranking, there are some audio descriptors that are highly used in the top 5 of contrary timbre attribute separation, and it was a predictable result, since this extracted features are not specially chosen by its relation to timbre. On the other hand, this particular result is only a single result that may not be reproducible with other datasets and/or other algorithms, but it helps to understand that there are some features that are highly used for this purpose and, there are other features that are not likely to be used by a classifier for this aim.

This extracted results become meaningful when we compare between different attributes and see similarities and differences. Many times, timbral attributes can be mixed, confused or misunderstood when we are not strongly familiar to them. This analysis may help to realize which are the common and differentiating elements between timbral attributes. It can become more intuitive if we analyze some examples:

Table 2: Selected features using $N = 5$ for Open/Close and Narrow/Broad pair of attributes data

Open/Close	Narrow/Broad
lowLevel spectral flux	lowLevel spectral rms
lowLevel pitch	lowLevel spectral decrease
lowLevel spectral decrease	lowLevel spectral energy
lowLevel spectral rms	lowLevel spectral energyband middle low
lowLevel spectral energy	lowLevel hfc

As we can see, obtaining these outputs from the feature selection algorithm, features in common and differentiating descriptors can be studied. For users not used to that vocabulary, Open could be very similar to Broad, or even non-distinguishable. Same could happen to Close and Narrow. With the analysis of the results shown in **table 2** we can get some clues about similarities and differences between classes. Actually, a new experiment has been done to eventually confirm this hypothesis. A new database has been created, including only Open and Broad data, and shared features in previous analysis (lowLevel spectral decrease, lowLevel spectral rms, lowLevel spectral energy) introduce quite poor information to separate between them because they have quite similar range of values in these features.

5.2 Number of attributes results

Apart from the previous results that show some interesting behaviors of the feature selection process applied to different classes and how timbral attributes share descriptors to discriminate against their contrary attribute, a parallel study has been conducted about the number of needed features to separate contrary timbral attributes.

A T-test experiment has been carried out to compare the performance of the classification task using a certain number of features against the same task using the full amount of audio descriptors. The same attribute selection algorithm has been used, using as an input parameter the desired number of features (increasing in 1 for each loop). The same classifying algorithm has been used too, and the T-test algorithm returns the statistical relevance compared to another experiment, determining if a certain increase of accuracy is statistically relevant or not. The result of this experiment helps to decide the amount of necessary features; i.e., if the accuracy of classification between dark and bright using all the extracted features is 91.82/100 and using 5 features the performance of the classifier is 90.30/100 but, even this losing of accuracy the, T-test determines that this difference is statistically irrelevant, 5 features would be enough to represent the same model as with all the features, and it would be much more efficient. This T-test could be also be conducted against the baseline, but it has been omitted since with 2 features, the accuracy is statistically relevant, so the results were minor for this particular task.

In the following table, an overview of a T-test experiment is shown:

Table 3: Number of appearances selecting 5.

Att.1	Att.2	2ft.	3ft.	4ft.	5ft.	8ft.	11ft.	14ft.	ALL	BL
Dark	Bright	86.19	88.72	89.56	90.30	90.48	91.04	91.32	91.82	64.5
Cold	Warm	77.52	81.27	80.95	83.37	85.70	86.21	86.72	87.36	60.75
Harsh	Sweet	68.90	76.82	78.63	81.14	82.21	82.40	83.51	86.02	50.31
Dry	Ressonant	88.72	91.19	93.17	93.26	93.08	92.99	94.05	93.84	61.99
Light	Heavy	84.54	84.48	85.14	85.37	86.88	87.49	88.26	87.85	65.34
Grainy	Pure	81.55	87.78	90.13	89.34	89.83	90.23	90.21	89.77	55.98
Coarse	Smooth	71.37	78.92	84.41	88.87	91.06	92.11	92.24	92.95	57.63
Closed	Open	79.29	82.05	82.60	84.46	86.08	86.42	86.24	84.46	51.08
Restrict	Free	74.61	82.78	84.06	84.50	84.86	84.29	84.01	85.96	50.57
Narrow	Broad	71.95	74.27	75.79	76.67	79.27	81.13	81.23	81.54	67.84

Analyzing these results, we can see that 6/10 classification tasks can reduce features to 5 or less. These results can be considered as encouraging since with significant feature reduction, the obtained results are as good as they are using all the extracted audio descriptors.

Once again, this results will depend on many factors as the dataset, the extracted features, the selected algorithms, and so on, but it helps to realize how much the number of features can be reduced for the task of timbre attributes discrimination.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

We can divide conclusions in two different points of view: if we look into the results looking inside each pair of attributes results, to achieve more local conclusions; or, comparing results among different pairs of attributes, to have a general overview of the whole thesis conclusions.

If we look inside a each pair of attributes, we have seen an example in the Results chapter. The presented example is a relevant illustration of what happens among pair of attributes and we can clearly assume after this results that, in this context, timbral attribute classes can be properly classified using a set of few audio features. It can be interpreted as that the information obtained by combining the right selected audio features is enough to separate timbral classes. Another interpretation, that could complement the first one, is that timbral attributes are strongly influenced by some descriptors of the audio, and nearly non-influenced by others; and different timbral attributes may be differently influenced by the same audio descriptors.

On the other hand, if we take a general overview of the different pair of attributes results, we can obtain interesting results; similar timbral attributes may tend to be influenced by similar audio descriptors. This assumption, created by evidences in results, leads to understand why some timbral attributes sound similar by having in common some influencing audio descriptors, and even getting similar values on these descriptors. Moreover, similar audio attributes can be hardly influenced by

different audio descriptors too, and it justifies not being the same timbral attribute.

All these conclusions, seen from a perspective of accomplishing the first hypothesis, lead to think that the assumption that audio descriptors might contain enough information to make feasible a classification model that correctly separate timbre attributes may be correct.

These conclusions are only truthful in this particular thesis and with this particular data. For that reason, some future work has to be done in this area to increase the knowledge on this topic.

Chapter 7

Contributions

The contributions of this master thesis are:

- A framework for audio preprocessing, features extraction and machine learning, including automated routines. All code is implemented and commented for further use.
- A set of audio features for classification of timbre.
- A tagged dataset of audio descriptors ready for use and future investigation.

All this code and information is open and will be included in <https://github.com/lladopedro>

Chapter 8

Future Work

Some ideas that could be implemented as future work in this topic are proposed to obtain deeper knowledge on this subject. As a first task, use bigger and more complex dataset would be interesting to test, since it would lead to more interesting results, denying the current conclusions, or realizing about limitations of the method. Another way to obtain more interesting results would be to analyze the data with other algorithms and try to improve the performance of the different algorithms in each step of the process.

Furthermore, this framework can be used to analyze the timbral attributes of other instruments. It would be interesting to obtain results to be compared against violin ones. Conclusions about timbre itself may be made if different instruments show evidences of similar conclusions.

The last proposed idea would be to convert this thesis framework into real-time. It would open a new dimension of applications, such as real-time feedback while music playing.

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Appendix A

First Appendix

Search Methods and Evaluators that have been used during the development of this thesis.

A.1 Search Methods

- Best First

Searches the space of attribute subsets by greedy hillclimbing augmented with a backtracking facility. Setting the number of consecutive non-improving nodes allowed controls the level of backtracking done. Best first may start with the empty set of attributes and search forward, or start with the full set of attributes and search backward, or start at any point and search in both directions (by considering all possible single attribute additions and deletions at a given point).

- Ranker

Ranks attributes by their individual evaluations. Use in conjunction with attribute evaluators (ReliefF, GainRatio, Entropy etc).

- GreedyStepwise

Performs a greedy forward or backward search through the space of attribute subsets. May start with no/all attributes or from an arbitrary point in the space. Stops when the addition/deletion of any remaining attributes results in a decrease in evaluation. Can also produce a ranked list of attributes by traversing the space from one side to the other and recording the order that attributes are selected.

A.2 Evaluation Methods

- InfoGainAttributeEval

Evaluates the worth of an attribute by measuring the information gain with respect to the class.

$$\text{InfoGain}(\text{Class}, \text{Attribute}) = H(\text{Class}) - H(\text{Class} \mid \text{Attribute}).$$

- CfsSubsetEval

Evaluates the worth of a subset of attributes by considering the individual predictive ability of each feature along with the degree of redundancy between them.

Subsets of features that are highly correlated with the class while having low inter-correlation are preferred.

For more information see:

M. A. Hall (1998). Correlation-based Feature Subset Selection for Machine Learning. Hamilton, New Zealand.

Appendix B

Second Appendix

Classification algorithms tested during the development of this thesis:

- `weka.classifiers.rules.ZeroR`

Class for building and using a 0-R classifier. Predicts the mean (for a numeric class) or the mode (for a nominal class).

- `weka.classifiers.rules.OneR`

Class for building and using a 1R classifier; in other words, uses the minimum-error attribute for prediction, discretizing numeric attributes. For more information, see:

R.C. Holte (1993). Very simple classification rules perform well on most commonly used datasets. *Machine Learning*. 11:63-91.

- `weka.classifiers.trees.J48`

Class for generating a pruned or unpruned C4.5 decision tree. For more information, see

Ross Quinlan (1993). *C4.5: Programs for Machine Learning*. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, San Mateo, CA.

- `weka.classifiers.functions.Logistic`

Class for building and using a multinomial logistic regression model with a ridge estimator.

There are some modifications, however, compared to the paper of leCessie and van Houwelingen(1992):

If there are k classes for n instances with m attributes, the parameter matrix B to be calculated will be an $m \times (k-1)$ matrix.

The probability for class j with the exception of the last class is

$$P_j(X_i) = \exp(X_i B_j) / ((\sum_{j=1..(k-1)} \exp(X_i * B_j)) + 1)$$

The last class has probability

$$1 - (\sum_{j=1..(k-1)} P_j(X_i)) = 1 / ((\sum_{j=1..(k-1)} \exp(X_i * B_j)) + 1)$$

The (negative) multinomial log-likelihood is thus:

$$L = -\sum_{i=1..n} [\sum_{j=1..(k-1)} (Y_{ij} * \ln(P_j(X_i))) + (1 - (\sum_{j=1..(k-1)} Y_{ij})) * \ln(1 - \sum_{j=1..(k-1)} P_j(X_i))] + \text{ridge} * (B^2)$$

In order to find the matrix B for which L is minimised, a Quasi-Newton Method is used to search for the optimized values of the $m \times (k-1)$ variables. Note that before we use the optimization procedure, we 'squeeze' the matrix B into a $m \times (k-1)$ vector. For details of the optimization procedure, please check `weka.core.Optimization` class.

Although original Logistic Regression does not deal with instance weights, we modify the algorithm a little bit to handle the instance weights.

For more information see:

le Cessie, S., van Houwelingen, J.C. (1992). Ridge Estimators in Logistic Regression. Applied Statistics. 41(1):191-201.

- `weka.classifiers.functions.SMO`

Implements John Platt's sequential minimal optimization algorithm for training a support vector classifier.

This implementation globally replaces all missing values and transforms nominal attributes into binary ones. It also normalizes all attributes by default. (In that case the coefficients in the output are based on the normalized data, not the original data — this is important for interpreting the classifier.)

Multi-class problems are solved using pairwise classification (aka 1-vs-1).

To obtain proper probability estimates, use the option that fits calibration models to the outputs of the support vector machine. In the multi-class case, the predicted probabilities are coupled using Hastie and Tibshirani's pairwise coupling method.

Note: for improved speed normalization should be turned off when operating on `SparseInstances`.

For more information on the SMO algorithm, see

J. Platt: Fast Training of Support Vector Machines using Sequential Minimal Optimization. In B. Schoelkopf and C. Burges and A. Smola, editors, *Advances in Kernel Methods - Support Vector Learning*, 1998.